

Mixed Chelate Complexes of Copper(II)

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IN continuation of our earlier work on mixed chelate complexes of several metals^{1,2} containing hetero-donor atoms, we report in this note, the preparation and characterization of copper(II) complexes containing Cu O₂NO and Cu S₂NO moiety.

Experimental

Bis diethyl (Et₂ dtc) and piperidyl (pdtc) dithiocarbamates of copper(II) were prepared by known method³. *Bis* acetylacetonato (acac), benzoylacetonato (bzac) and dibenzoylmethanato (bzbz) copper(II) were also prepared as per published method⁴.

Reaction of bis β-diketonato Copper(II) with Picolinic acid :

To a methanolic solution of Cu(acac)₂, an ethanolic solution of picolinic acid was added in 1 : 1 molar ratio. The resulting solution was refluxed for two hours and the separated complex was suction filtered, washed with methanol followed by ether and dried *in vacuo*. In case of Cu(bzac)₂ and Cu(bzbz)₂, the reactions were carried out in chloroform medium.

Reaction of bis dithiocarbamato Copper(II) with Picolinic acid :

Bis dithiocarbamato copper(II) compounds were treated separately with picolinic acid in 1 : 1 molar ratio in chloroform medium. The resulting solution was refluxed for one hour. The separated complexes were suction filtered, washed with ether and dried *in vacuo*.

Copper and sulphur were estimated by standard methods. Infrared spectra in the range 5000-650 cm⁻¹ were recorded on Nujol mulls using Unicam SP 200 double beam spectrophotometer. The

electronic spectra in chloroform or acetone solution were recorded using Unicam SP 500 spectrophotometer. The magnetic susceptibilities were determined at room temperature on solid specimens using Gouy method. Diamagnetic corrections were made using Pascal's constants. The molar conductance was measured in ~10⁻³M solution using Toshniwal conductivity bridge, type CLO102 and a dip type cell.

Results and Discussion

The analytical, molar conductance and magnetic susceptibility data are recorded in Table 1. Infrared and electronic spectral data are recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 2—INFRARED AND ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL DATA (in cm⁻¹) OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)

	β-diketonate		Picolinic acid		λ _{max}
	νC=O	νC=C	νCOO ⁻		
Cu(acac)(Pyca)	1590	1540	1610, 1650		16500
Cu(bzac)(Pyca)	1605	1550	1615, 1645		16500
Cu(bzbz)(Pyca)	1605	1555	1650		16600
	dithiocarbamate		Picolinic acid		
	νC-N	ν _{as} C-S	ν _s C-S	νCOO ⁻	
Cu(Et ₂ -dtc)(Pyca)	1510	995	710	1605, 1650	16400
Cu(pdte)(Pyca)	1510	995	710	1610, 1650	16400

The low molar conductance values ($\Lambda_M = 4.0-6.0$ mhos cm² mole⁻¹) of mixed chelate complexes in DMF suggest them to be non-conducting indicating their non-electrolytic nature. The magnetic susceptibility measurements indicate that all the complexes are paramagnetic as expected for a 3d⁹ cupric ion. The observed moments (~1.86 B.M.) are close to spin only value for one unpaired electron and suggest square planar structure for the complexes⁵.

Infrared Spectra :

The infrared spectral data are quite informative. The relevant infrared absorption bands due to the coordinated chelates in the complexes with their possible assignments are given in the Table 2. The νC-N and ν_{as}C-S bands due to dithiocarbamates at ~1500 and ~1000 cm⁻¹ clearly indicate that they

TABLE 1—ANALYSES, MELTING POINTS, MOLAR CONDUCTANCE AND MAGNETIC MOMENT VALUES OF MIXED CHELATE COMPLEXES OF COPPER(II)

Compounds	Colour	m.p. °C	Λ _M (mhos)	μ _{eff} B.M.	%Cu		%S	
					Found	Cal	Found	Cal
1. Cu(acac)(Pyca)	Blue	>300	4.58	1.85	22.01	22.33	—	—
2. Cu(bzac)(Pyca)	Blue	290	5.62	1.86	18.25	18.33	—	—
3. Cu(bzbz)(Pyca)	Blue	>300	5.32	1.86	15.13	15.55	—	—
4. Cu(Et ₂ -dtc)(Pyca)	Blue	>300	5.50	1.84	18.28	19.05	19.51	19.18
5. Cu(pdte)(Pyca)	Light green	225	6.15	1.84	18.15	18.98	18.67	18.52

NOTES

are coordinated to the metal ion through both the sulphur atoms⁶. In the β -diketonato complexes the bands due to $\nu\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $\nu\text{C}=\text{C}$ were observed in the region $\sim 1600\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $\sim 1570\text{ cm}^{-1}$ respectively as expected, indicating the presence of coordinated carbonyl group of β -diketone⁷. Picolinic acid (Pyca) shows an absorption band between $1750\text{--}1700\text{ cm}^{-1}$ which was assigned⁸ to $\nu\text{C}-\text{O}$ of the free $-\text{COOH}$ group. In the complexes under investigation, the band due to free $-\text{COOH}$ was found to be absent. Other bands due to $\nu_{\text{as}}\text{COO}^-$ and pyridine ring were found to be present at 1610 and 1650 cm^{-1} as observed by Fowles *et al.*⁹. This suggests that picolinic acid is coordinated to the metal ion through oxygen and nitrogen atoms.

Electronic Spectra :

Though three transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$, ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{B}_{2g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ are expected for copper(II) complexes they are very close in energy and often give rise to one broad band envelop. Sacconi⁸ and Meek and Ehrhardt¹⁰ have observed that square planar complexes have complex broad band at relatively higher frequencies $\sim 16000\text{ cm}^{-1}$. The regular tetrahedral complexes of copper(II) show no d-d absorption bands in the region $10000\text{--}20000\text{ cm}^{-1}$.¹¹ The spectra of all the complexes now studied display a broad band around 16000 cm^{-1} which may be assigned to a combination of the two transitions ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{A}_{1g}$ and ${}^2\text{B}_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{E}_g$ in D_{4h} symmetry¹². The position of this absorption band (16000 cm^{-1}) is in agreement with those generally observed for planar copper(II) complexes¹³⁻¹⁶. Thus, the compounds reported now are definitely four coordinated mixed chelate complexes of copper(II) with presumably square planar geometry.

References

1. A. K. DAS and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *Chem. and Ind.* 1975, 792.
2. B. PRADHAN and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **55**, 226.
3. R. N. DASH and D. V. RAMANA RAO, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1975, **52**, 1009.
4. T. SHIGEMATSU, M. TABUSHI, M. MATSUI and M. MUNAKATA, *Bull. Chem. Soc., Japan*, 1968, **41**, 2656.
5. L. SACCONI and M. CLAPOLINI, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1964, 278.
6. R. M. GOLDING, C. M. HARRIS, K. J. JESSOP and W. C. TENNANT, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1972, **25**, 2567.
7. K. NAKAMOTO, "Infrared Spectra of Inorganic and Coordination Compounds", John Wiley and Sons, New York, 1969.
8. M. G. B. DREW, G. W. A. FOWLES, R. W. MATTHEWS and R. A. WALTON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1968, **91**, 7769.
9. G. W. A. FOWLES, R. W. MATTHEWS and R. A. WALTON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, A 1968, 1108.
10. D. W. MERK and S. A. EHRHARDT, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1965, **4**, 584.
11. A. B. P. LEVER, "Inorganic Electronic Spectroscopy", Elsevier, Amsterdam, 1968, p. 359.

12. B. N. FIGGIS, "Introduction to Ligand Fields", Interscience, New York, 1967, p. 316.
13. L. E. ORGEL, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1956, **23**, 6.
14. W. BYERS, A. B. P. LEVER and R. V. PARISH, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 1835.
15. N. M. KARAYANNIS, C. M. MIKULSKI, L. L. PVTLEWSKI and M. M. LABES, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1972, **34**, 3139.
16. K. GOPALKRISHAN, UMA CHUDASAMA and P. K. BHATTACHARYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1979, **56**, 752.

Determination of the Stability Constants of 2-Hydroxy-1-Naphthalidene-Monoethanolamine Complexes with Pr^{3+} , Nd^{3+} , Gd^{3+} , Dy^{3+} and Y^{3+}

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IN the present communication the successive stability constants of the complexes of 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-monoethanolamine with various trivalent metal ions have been determined potentiometrically following the Calvin-Bjerrum pH titration technique as adopted by Irving and Rossotti¹.

Experimental

The ligand 2-hydroxy-1-naphthalidene-monoethanolamine was synthesized by method described in literature and repeatedly crystallized from ethanol to get an analytically pure compound with m.p. 153° .²

The experimental details are the same as described in the earlier communication³. The experimental technique of Irving and Rossotti¹ was applied to find out the values of \bar{n} and pL . The titrations were performed in duplicate to test for reproducibility.

Results and Discussion

It may be mentioned here, that the ligand does not undergo hydrolysis under the experimental conditions described. This was indicated by the rapid attainment of equilibrium during titrations and by absence of any significant drift in pH, even after two hours. This was also corroborated by taking T.L.C. of a sample titration mixture, from time to time.

In the ligand it is the phenolic (OH) group, which takes part in the complex formation, and the proton is replaced from it by metal ions during chelation. As only one proton per ligand molecule is liberated during complexation, 'Y' the number of